

Supplementary Figure S3. Growth curves of WT (green circle) $\Delta aceE$ (dark grey square) and $\Delta aceF$ (grey triangle) in LB media grown (A) aerobically, (B) anaerobically, or (C) anaerobically supplemented with 50mM fumarate. Data represent the average and SEM for three independent biological replicates.